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IEEE International Network Generations Roadmap Satellite Edition 2023 Updates

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What is the International Network Generations Roadmap?

<https://futurenetworks.ieee.org/roadmap>

About the IEEE International Network Generations Roadmap (INGR)

The purpose of the International Network Generations Roadmap (INGR) is to stimulate an industry-wide dialogue to address the many facets and challenges of the development and deployment of 5G in a well-coordinated and comprehensive manner, while also looking beyond 5G by laying out a technology roadmap with 3-year, 5-year, and 10-year horizon. Future network technologies (5G, 6G, etc.) are expected to enable fundamentally new applications that will transform the way humanity lives, works, and engages with its environment. INGR, created by experts across industry, government and academia, is designed to help guide operators, regulators, manufacturers, researchers, and other interested parties involved in developing these new communication technology ecosystems. Each chapter is peer-reviewed by internal industry experts, then sent out for external review by subject matter experts, and finally receives an editorial review before being finalized for publication.

Development of the INGR has produced a technical community that fosters the exchange of ideas, sharing of research, setting of standards, and identification, development, and maturation of system drivers, system specifications, use cases, and supported applications. As work continues, **new experts are encouraged to participate**, to evolve and strengthen this crucial document. Join us!

Working Group and Contact Information

Working Group Teams

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Why NTN?

- 37% of world's population still lacks high-speed internet access
- Current terrestrial networks cannot guarantee access to the internet for passengers on aircraft, ships or high-speed trains, highways, and remote areas
- Satellite systems can complement 5G and 6G terrestrial wireless networks to satisfy these requirements
- Really, Non-Terrestrial-Networks (NTN) which includes other platforms in addition to satellites
 - Low Altitude Platforms (LAPs)
 - High Altitude Platforms (HAPs)
 - Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs)

Type of NTN	Name	Approximate orbital altitude
LAP	Low Altitude Platforms (UAVs belong to this category)	100 m – 1 km
HAP	High Altitude Platforms	1 km – 100 km
LEO	Low Earth Orbit satellites	100 km – 1000 km
MEO	Medium Earth Orbit satellites	1000 km – 2000 km
GEO	Geostationary Orbit Satellites	36000 km
HEO	Highly Elliptical Orbit satellites	100 km to > 36000 km

Report Topics and Scope

<i>Topic</i>	<i>Scope</i>
Applications and Services	5G/6G satellite applications for urban, rural, and remote areas. There is a need to expand from the current 5G to the future 6G applications and services. New services, such as space-based hosting services or lowering the latency of web services over Non-Terrestrial Networks (NTN) can be considered.
Reference Architectures	A total of 12 use cases are discussed, including backhaul services over LEO / MEO / GEO satellites, UAV, and HAPs. Further, 22 use cases for direct access to satellite and NTN networks are also discussed. Six physical layer scenarios for LEO-based satellite-IoT scenarios were also discussed. Three reference architectures of 5G/6G satellites, including non-virtualized for the near-term (3 years), separately virtualized for the mid-term (5 years), and integrated virtualized for the long-term (10 years) are described.
mmWave Adoption in Satellite System	The use of the mmWave band (Q/V/W) has been investigated to cope with the spectrum demand of the next generation of satellite networks.
Antenna and Payload	Various antenna systems for ground stations, satellite feeder links, user links, inter-satellite links, and end-users are briefly discussed.
Machine Learning and Artificial Intelligence	Classification of ML techniques for non-terrestrial networks is described.
Edge Computing	Computation offloading, MEC caching, deployment, and orchestration are discussed.
QoS / QoE	QoS and QoE are discussed in terms of propagation delay and architecture.
Security	Secure air interface, network architecture, trust management, end-to-end security management, etc., are addressed in this report.
Network Management	Mobility management, radio resource management, and routing are described. SDN and NVF are discussed.
Standardization	The current status of 3GPP, ITU, ETSI, and IEEE standardization activities on satellite 5G/6G, including NT, are discussed.

2023 Report Key Contributions (p1 of 3)

- The INGR Satellite Working Group raised further challenges and presented possible solutions for the evolution of satellite systems from 5G to 6G, with particular reference to satellites at 5G/6G backhaul and direct-access satellite services
- Architectures including satellites, in conjunction with HAPs and UAVs can provide equivalent 5G/6G services
- Applications suitable for 5G augmentation (eMBB and mMTC cases)
- New applications of space-based hosting and LEO-satellite-based services
- Provided several use cases covering
 - Satellite Networks as backhaul for 6G Terrestrial Networks
 - Direct Access Satellite Networks
 - Satellite IoT
- Three reference architectures
 - RA-1 – non-Virtualized 5G-Satellite Networks (near term development)
 - RA-2 – separate-Virtualized 5G-Satellite Networks (medium term development)
 - RA-3 – integrated-Virtualized 6G-Satellite Networks (long term development)

2023 Report Key Contributions(p2 of 3)

- Provided analysis on the PHY layer to support high performance networks
 - New modulation schemes
 - MIMO antennas and reconfigurable multifeed antennas with electronic beam-steering
 - mmWave frequency (propagation study conducted)
 - Optical communications for satellite-to-satellite links, satellite-to-ground links, and satellite-to-aerials link
 - Increases link capacity
 - Better security
- The use of AI/ML to optimize routing and path selection, handover schemes, PHY adaptation, security etc.
- Inclusion of Multi-access Edge Computing (MEC) – can reduce the frequency of communications via satellite hops, thus supporting critical functions for 5G/6G offloading and caching
 - With the future of MEC implemented on-board satellites (ie: dedicated services from the sky)
- QoS and QoE approach terrestrial networks by using mega-LEO constellations and advanced networking MEC, caching, and network slicing

2023 Report Key Contributions (p3 of 3)

- Network management, mobility management, radio resource management, routing, softwarization, and virtualization of the satellite network need to integrate aerial components with 5G/6G terrestrial systems
 - Maintaining a consistent addressing scheme
 - Performing efficient and scalable handovers
 - Avoidance of interference problems
- Current standardization (3GPP) does not adequately cover mega-LEO constellations, HAPs, or UAVs
- Zero Trust Security – treats each network element as a source of attack (ie: trust must be developed and learned continuously)

Working Group Recommendations (p1 of 2)

- **Identification of architectures with multiple connectivity types (UAVs, HAPs, MEO, LEO)**
- **Achieve system interoperability not only with terrestrial 5G/6G, but also with aerial components of other operators**
- MIMO communications will increase capacity and improve the physical layer security
- **mmWave communications via satellite with vulnerabilities due to weather and large Doppler shifts from LEO**
- **Complex antennas with multi-feed and electronic beam steering capability**
- MEC in space as onboard resources improve and eventual implementation of gNodeB and UPF functionalities in the space segment
- Dataset generation, collection, and emulation by considering different satellite reference architectures – initial investigation of ML techniques

Working Group Recommendations (p2 of 2)

- Mega-LEO constellations entail significant complexity to be managed. AI/ML can provide possible new methods to solve complex problems such as routing, resource allocation, cross-layer optimization, and handover decision in a scalable and efficient way
- Additional work is needed to address multi-layer systems, including GEO, MEO, and LEO, as well as the role of UAVs and HAPs
- Integrated hybrid optical-radio system will play a key role in providing the capacity, resilience, and security that new 6G services will demand.
 - QKD system can be understood as a particular use case of hybrid optical-radio systems

Reference Architecture – RA1

Near Term (3 years out)

Figure 8. Reference Architecture-1: Non-Virtualized 5G Satellite Networks

- 5G terrestrial networks use the existing satellite networks as a traffic tunnel or bent-pipe scheme for carrying traffic.
- The control and data traffic over the N1, N2, and N3 interfaces (defined in 3GPP TS 23.501), are tunneled to the 5G control and data planes
- RA-1 essentially utilizes the non-3GPP communication for the 5G user traffic

Reference Architecture – RA2

Medium Term (5 years out)

Figure 10. Reference Architecture-2

- The satellite network is a virtualized network infrastructure similar yet separated from the terrestrial 5G virtualized network
- Satellite network virtualization faces different network challenges, network function requirements, and implementation scenarios

Reference Architecture – RA3

Long Term (10 years out)

Figure 11. Reference Architecture-3

- In the long term, the two networks will evolve into an integrated virtualized 5G-satellite network system
- Single MANO
- The satellite segments will consist of LEO, MEO, and GEO satellites, as well as UAVs and HAPs
- The integrated MANO module of the network is responsible for carrying out resource management, routing packets, channel management, slice management, edge computing decisions, and federated functions

mmWave Adoption

- mmWave adoption will be able to meet the growing demands for capacity/datarates due to large available spectrum
- mmWave adoption comes with significant challenges
 - Atmospheric/meteorological effects
 - Reduce power and efficiency in high power amplifiers
 - Cost (not commercially viable, yet)
- Mitigation
 - Ground station diversity
 - Robust adaptive error correction codes
 - Dynamic link layer adaptation – meteorologically dependent
 - Resilient communications waveform – OFDM
 - Harmonization around frequency bands
 - Commercial interest
 - Utilize other NTN elements in the network

Figure 12. Attenuation in dB/km of the Atmospheric Gasses: Oxygen, Water Vapor, and Total Pressure = 1 013.25 hPa; Temperature = 15°C; Water Vapor Density = 7.5 g/m³

Figure 13. Rain Attenuation in dB/km Across Frequency for the Rainfall Rates of 2.5 mm/h

Table 15. Uplink, Downlink, and Available Spectrum for the mmWave through Satellite (per ITU-R Regulations)

Frequency Band	Uplink	Downlink	Available Uplink Spectrum	Available Downlink Spectrum
Q	42.5-43.5 GHz 47.2-50.2 GHz	37.5-42.5 GHz 47.5-47.9 GHz 48.2-48.54 GHz 49.44-50.2 GHz	4 GHz	6.32 GHz
V	50.4-51.4 GHz	71-75 GHz	1 GHz	4 GHz
W	81-86 GHz	75-76 GHz	5 GHz	1 GHz

NTN asset usage to counter link degradation

Figure 22. Use Case-1

Figure 24. Use Case-3

Transmit via a cross-link to avoid meteorological outage

Figure 32. Use Case-11

Find optimal path through NTN elements

Antenna and Payload (p1 of 3)

Table 20. Overall Needs

<i>Needs</i>	<i>Description</i>
Capacity	Higher communications capacities are required, both per user and on aggregate.
Robustness	Under all conditions, the antenna system must be reliable and interoperable with other satellite provider assets.
Security	System elements must not impair communications security.

Capacity Challenges (near term):

- Wide operating bandwidth required on the antennas
 - Need for interoperability between networks and service providers
- There is an associated Size, Weight, and Power (SWaP) and cost penalty for the wide bandwidth
 - Can limit the deployment of technologies needed to advance these satellite systems

Antenna and Payload (p2 of 3)

Table 20. Overall Needs

<i>Needs</i>	<i>Description</i>
Capacity	Higher communications capacities are required, both per user and on aggregate.
Robustness	Under all conditions, the antenna system must be reliable and interoperable with other satellite provider assets.
Security	System elements must not impair communications security.

Capacity Challenges (Medium Term):

- Tracking satellites in same or different orbits requires multi-axis scanning capability, over a wide bandwidth
 - Very challenging
 - Needed for both ground and space segments

Antenna and Payload (p3 of 3)

Table 20. Overall Needs

<i>Needs</i>	<i>Description</i>
Capacity	Higher communications capacities are required, both per user and on aggregate.
Robustness	Under all conditions, the antenna system must be reliable and interoperable with other satellite provider assets.
Security	System elements must not impair communications security.

Capacity Challenges (Long Term):

- The ability to track and perform a seamless handover (make-before-break) to a satellite outside of its network over a wide frequency bandwidth
 - Antenna to support multibeam
- Applies to both space and ground segment

Antenna and Payload - Robustness

Table 20. Overall Needs

<i>Needs</i>	<i>Description</i>
Capacity	Higher communications capacities are required, both per user and on aggregate.
Robustness	Under all conditions, the antenna system must be reliable and interoperable with other satellite provider assets.
Security	System elements must not impair communications security.

Robustness Challenges:

- In a network with multiple NTN assets, the opportunity for interference disrupting service increases
 - Advanced beamforming networks to steer a null in direction of the interferers would be useful
- Increasing the operating bandwidth to avoid atmospheric effects
 - Switching to lower mmWave bands

Antenna and Payload - Security

Table 20. Overall Needs

<i>Needs</i>	<i>Description</i>
Capacity	Higher communications capacities are required, both per user and on aggregate.
Robustness	Under all conditions, the antenna system must be reliable and interoperable with other satellite provider assets.
Security	System elements must not impair communications security.

Security Challenges:

- Potential eavesdropping is not a major issue due to robust network security
- Interference (intentional) that can limit or disrupt performance
 - Simpler to do due to the wide bandwidth of operation

NASA Wideband Development – NTN (p1 of 4)

<https://ntrs.nasa.gov/citations/20210020202>

Terminal Overview and Approach

Goal: Support transition of NASA missions to use of commercial space relay services

Drivers / Timeline:

- NASA decision to cut off new TDRSS commitments represents a major transition point for the agency. Commercial capability needs to be established prior to cut-off date

Approach:

- Develop a prototype user terminal to support low latency space relay links across NASA/Commercial/DoD assets
- Operation from 17.7 – 31 GHz also captures TDRSS and near-Earth DTE Ka bands
- Focus on integration of commercially available product lines or, where products do not exist, focus on the development of technology gap areas toward the realization of a flight product
- Conduct a combination of early ground-based and space-based experiments to demonstrate proof-of-concept wideband terminal operations
- Invest in parallel development paths: Glenn Research Center (GRC) and Johns Hopkins Applied Physics Lab (APL)

NASA Wideband Development – NTN (p2 of 4)

<https://ntrs.nasa.gov/citations/20210020202>

Historically, interoperability among civil space agencies was achieved through collaboration within the Consultative Committee for Space Data Systems (CCSDS)

- > Like-minded organizations – common objectives
- > Cross-support of spacecraft reduces risk

Going forward: NASA is pushing to adopt more commercial standards as the LEO commercial space market matures:

- > Engage with 3GPP
- > Bring 5G communications capabilities to space missions
- > Support “one of many” objective

Achieving Interoperability across networks and providers

- Continue to support civil space standards
- Adopt commercial standards
- Engage with industry
- Pursue Wideband Multilingual User Terminals
- 5G Opportunity

NASA Wideband Development – NTN (p3 of 4)

<https://ntrs.nasa.gov/citations/20210020202>

3GPP and Non-Terrestrial Networking

3GPP is developing 5G Release 17, and planning Release 18, both of which will include non-terrestrial network (NTN), or satellite components

Convergence of satellite and terrestrial represents an opportunity for NASA and other space users

NASA became a guest member of 3GPP in 2020

Three objectives for NASA engagement in 3GPP:

- Understand scope of releases and implications for space users
- Make a case for inclusion of the space user as a unique use case for 5G
- Advocate for the evolution of 5G and NTN to support space user needs

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NASA Wideband Development – NTN (p4 of 4)

<https://ntrs.nasa.gov/citations/20210020202>

Beyond Earth...

NASA's interest extends beyond NTN and near-Earth space to using 3GPP as part of future Lunar communication architectures

- Lunar surface use cases identified require kilometer+ distances exceeding 802.11 capability
- Analogous to terrestrial use cases that are supported by 4G/LTE standards

NASA awarded a Lunar Surface Innovation Initiative Technology Demonstration to Nokia, partnering with Intuitive Machines to demonstrate a 4G/LTE base station and user radio on the moon

Future 3GPP releases that address satellite-to-satellite and satellite-to-surface use could also be directly applied to future lunar relay systems

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Questions?